

BUSINESS 01

The stages of business creation

An overview of all the steps involved in starting a business,
their meaning and interdependences

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Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

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Target

 BUSINESS **MODULE 1**

The stages of business creation

In this module you will get an overview of all the steps involved in starting a business. You will learn the meaning of each step and its interdependence with the other steps.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 Eliminate preconceived ideas about starting a business
- 2 Why creating a business is an iterative approach
- 3 Knowledge of the different steps to follow when creating a business
- 4 The three pillars to consider when creating a business

Chapters of this module

1 Some basics about the business creations steps

2 Global presentation of the 8 different steps to follow when creating a business

3 The three pillars of the business creation

4 The iterative approach of the business creation

Some basics about the steps of business creation

Let's start with some basics about the different steps you need to take to start your business.

These basics will help you to better understand the following chapters.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 | Eliminate preconceived ideas about starting a business

Basics

- There is no ideal duration in the way of creating your own business. You can spend 3 months, 6 months or more than a year. The time you spend in planning your business launch depends on various variables: the daily time you dedicate for that project, your energy, the type of business you want to run, the stakeholders your business depends on (providers, bank...), etc.
- No step is more complicated, lengthy or more/less important than the other. The time spent on each step and the ease/difficulty working on it depends on: your skills, your motivations, the time of business you want to implement, etc.

Basics

- Skipping one step because you estimate it's not important can be highly detrimental for your business, because all of the steps are interdependent and follow a common thread.
- Consequently, we fully advise you to follow ALL the steps and to move on to the next one ONCE you understand well the current one.
- Furthermore, we recommend you to put away your misconceptions about your abilities to learn and understand one or some of the topics covered by this business training course. The training units of the business training course are all skills levels and without pre-requisites.

Chapter summary

1

There is no ideal path to follow when creating a business.

2

The best path is your own pace of learning.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Chapter summary

1

You are now able to overcoming major false beliefs about the process of creating a business.

2

You will be able to identify the main pitfalls to avoid when you start working on your business project.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUSINESS | **MODULE 1** | **CHAPTER 2**

Global presentation of the 8 different steps

Starting a business requires going through different stages. Each of them requires different skills and knowledge. It's time to get to the bottom of it.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 What are the different steps to take when creating a business.
- 2 What are the different skills to be developed when working on these steps.

Global presentation of the 8 different steps

Now it's time to see what is awaiting you for the next months.

When creating a business, the first question you ask to yourself is: where to start? What do we do concretely in order to launch a business?

It's what we will see in this chapter.

The 8 steps

The 8 steps

The 8 steps

As you can see in these two illustrations, regarding the step by which you will be concerned, you'll be supposed to work on one or several pillars.

It means that your field of analysis and reflection will be different according to the step. Sometimes you will lead an introspective work about yourself, sometimes you will make some environmental analysis like observation of your competitors and at other times, you will be working on technical topics like making financial plan.

These three pillars will be seen in more detail in the next chapter.

Did you know?

Working on technical aspects of your business (like financial plan or market study e.g.) is only a small part of the time you will spend on building your business project.

Chapter summary

1

There are 8 main steps to take when starting a business.

2

Each stage required the development of different skills and knowledge.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Chapter summary

1

You are more comfortable with the different steps you will take to build your business project.

2

You are more aware that starting a business involves different types of work: introspective work and technical work.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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BUSINESS | MODULE 1 | CHAPTER 3

The three pillars

Depending on the stage of business creation you are in, you will be working on at least one of these three areas: you, your business structure and your business environment. Let's get into the details.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 Building a business requires work on different levels: personal, interpersonal and technical ones.
- 2 A solid business construction implies that each pillar is taken into account.

The three pillars

In each step, the way you build your project is related to one of these pillars:

- You
- Your business environment (and your business' stakeholders)
- Your business structure

Let's get into more details about these pillars.

YOU

The first pillar you will be working on is YOU. It means the relation between YOU and the two other pillars.

- What are your financial goals (wage goal e.g.)? Are you willing to work for no wage at the beginning? For how long?
- What is the maximum working hours/week you're willing to accept?
- What skills do you need to implement or develop in order to run your business?
- How much financial risks are you willing to take?
- How comfortable are you with managing people?

You will be the brain and the fuel of your future business. The way your business will grow depends

on your capacity to take decisions as well as your know-how skills.

If you are not all clear, coherent, with what you want, what you're able to do and how you want to do things, you risk to face unexpected detrimental experiences.

What more uncomfortable than finding out that to grow your business you need to make financial investments you're not willing to?

What more uncomfortable than finding out that to sustain your business you need to work much more than expected?

What more uncomfortable than finding out that your technical skills are not adequate with your job?

YOU

For these reasons, to start on the right foot and limit unpleasant surprises once your business launched, working seriously on the YOU and the «coherence between entrepreneur and business project» with the BUSINESS Module 2 is the first step to follow.

**BUSINESS
MODULE 2**

Did you know?

Creating a business often requires an important work of introspection.

You will spend a lot of time thinking about your motivations, your strengths or your slots for improvements for instance.

YOUR BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT

The second pillar you'll working on is your business environment.

We just saw that YOU are the core piece of the adventure that is launching a business. But you are not the only piece.

In fact, you will be in contact with numerous external players like your competitors, your customers, your suppliers, your bank, your partners (graphic/website designer e.g.).

Creating a business without taking into account these numerous stakeholders is taking the risk to create an activity outside the reality ».

- Who are your competitors?
- What types of products do they sell ?
- What are their prices ?
- Their strengths ?
- Their weaknesses ?
- Who are your future customers?
- What they want?
- How much would they pay for your services?

Answering this type of questions will help you to build a business that fits well with your future market characteristics.

YOUR BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT

If you don't know who will be part of your future environment, if you don't know their characteristics, what and how they do things, you won't be able to evaluate and build your business regarding what already exists.

You won't be able to identify what makes you different, what is your added-value and how to leverage your strengths.

In fact, you won't be able to make a business « custom made » with what is expected in your market (=what your customers want).

 Did you know?

One of the basics of business creation is analysing your environment in order to fit as much as possible to its characteristics and particularly : customers' needs and competitors' differentiation.

YOUR BUSINESS STRUCTURE

The third pillar you'll be working on is your business itself, in other words, your business structure.

Being coherent with who you are and what you want to do and then analyse your business environment are very important steps.

But then, it's time to put some content in what your business will be.

- What your prices will be?
- What financial structure to start with?
- What will be your communication campaign?
- What ranges of products will you sell and through which distribution channels?

Did you know?

Having an idea and giving a structure to an idea are very different.

Having an idea makes you have a potential business project.

Giving a structure to your idea makes you having a business already launched.

The official registration is just the final result of the structure you gave to your initial idea.

The three pillars

Throughout the different steps, these three pillars will represent a sort of anchor that will help you to think in hindsight regarding your business.

Thinking in hindsight is very important because it helps you to think your business more “wisely” with more coherence and objectivity.

It helps you limit your getting overwhelmed by your feelings and emotions.

Using these three pillars as an anchor will lead you to think “Ok, I just worked on that topic. It involves a personal and a technical work. How is the coherence between what I want/can do in this business and what this technical work shows it’s required from me?”.

Chapter summary

1

The three pillars to work on when creating a business are you, your business structure and your business environment.

2

Questioning about each of these three pillars when building your business project allows you to step back and see things with more perspective.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Chapter summary

1

You are more aware that starting a business is a multifaceted process that requires different kinds of thinking.

2

You understand that the technical and financial aspects of your business are only part of the process of your business creation.

What is next?

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MODULE 2](#)

The iterative approach

Creating a business is not a straight line road. Several round trips and retrograde steps are part of the game. In this chapter, you will learn the concept of iterative approach.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 Starting a business is not like a to-do list.
- 2 Business creation process is not linear, it is iterative.

The iterative approach

This chapter will show you that creating a business is rarely a quiet river.

Most people think that creating a business looks like a TO DO LIST principle: you check one box and move to the next one.

In fact, creating a business is the opposite.

The iterative approach

As you noticed, the business creation process is not linear. In fact, building a business is an iterative process.

In other words, creating a business consists in repetitive testing and adjustments in order to reach a desired result at.

Working on one pillar or step leads you to make some adjustments to what you did with the previous pillar/step. For instance, working on step 5 will probably lead you to make adjustments to step 3 and so forth.

Let's take a look at the next illustration.

Lines of research and reflection (several iterations until general synthesis)

The iterative approach

As you can see , creating a business is constant comings and goings between the different steps and pillars.

In fact, from the beginning of the idea to the official registration of the company you won't stop:

- Working on you : motivations, goals, skills, etc.,
- Observing and analysing your environment and stakeholders,
- Make your business idea more and more concrete and structured,
- Make adjustments to what you already worked on.

Chapter summary

1

Creating a business is about testing different approaches and then making adjustments.

2

The business creation is not a linear process. It's the opposite of a to-do list.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Chapter summary

1

You know what an iterative method of building a project is and why starting a business is part of it.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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Module summary

1

In summary, it's important to remember that the steps you will follow are not chronological.

2

The way of building your business project won't be linear and regular. You will experience plenty of regressions and backward steps.

3

When building your business project, you never stop working on your personal feelings, on your business environment and your business organization.

4

Throughout your business creation steps, these 3 pillars are in constant evolution in order to become, weeks after weeks stronger more coherent between them.

Go to the quiz

Hope you have a better insight of what is expecting you for the next weeks. But know worry, things are simpler than they seem.

To finish with this topic, we invite you to go to the quiz to assess your understanding of this training unit.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 BUSINESS MODULE 1 The business creation steps

The ideal time period in which to build your business project is:

- 1 year
- There is no ideal time period
- 3 months
- 6 months

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

1

Knowledge of the different steps to follow to create a business.

2

Knowledge of the false beliefs and the appropriate mind-set about creating a business.

What is next?

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